

Dihydroisocoumarins. Part VI. Further Application of the Reaction with *N*-Bromosuccinimide: A Route to 6-Methoxyisocoumarin

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Starting with methyl 2-methoxycarbonyl-5-methoxyphenylacetate, 6-methoxyisochroman has been synthesised and oxidised to 3,4-dihydro-6-methoxyisocoumarin which has been converted into 6-methoxyisocoumarin with the aid of NBS.

Kamal *et al.*¹ failed to synthesise 6-methoxyisocoumarin (IV) as they could not effect decarboxylation of 6-methoxyisocoumarin-4-carboxylic acid, prepared by condensing methyl 2-methoxycarbonyl-5-methoxyphenylacetate (I: R=CO₂Me; R₁=CH₂(CO₂Me) with methyl formate, followed by cyclisation of the resulting hydroxy-methylene product and subsequent hydrolysis.

Starting with homophthalates, a new route to isocoumarin synthesis² was developed in this laboratory which involved preparation of dihydroisocoumarins as intermediates and their interaction with NBS. Adopting the same sequence of reactions, 6-methoxyisocoumarin has been synthesised as follows: 3-Methoxydihydrocinnamic acid³ was cyclised with PPA to 5-methoxyindan-1-one in 90% yield by modifying the procedures described earlier^{4,5}. Its 2-oximino derivative⁶ was converted into 2-carboxy-5-methoxyphenylacetic acid (I: R=CO₂H; R₁=CH₂CO₂H) and was esterified to yield methyl 2-methoxycarbonyl-5-methoxyphenylacetate² (I: R=CO₂Me; R₁=CH₂CO₂Me). Lithium aluminium hydride reduction of the ester afforded 2-hydroxymethyl-5-methoxyphenethyl alcohol (I:R=CH₂OH; R₁=CH₂CH₂OH) which on cyclodehydration with phosphorus pentoxide in boiling benzene or distillation *in vacuo* with potassium bisulphate furnished 6-methoxyisochroman (II). Subsequent oxidation with selenium dioxide or preferably with chromic acid yielded 3,4-dihydro-6-methoxyisocoumarin (III: R=H) which on interaction with NBS provided 4-bromo-3,4-dihydro-6-methoxyisocoumarin (III: R=Br). Dehydrobromination with refluxing triethylamine finally afforded 6-methoxyisocoumarin (IV).

(I)

(II)

(III)

(IV)

1. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 3375.
2. Srivastava and Chaudhury, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1962, 27, 4337.
3. Ingold and Piggot, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 1469.
4. Birch *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1952, 1768.
5. Bone and Cort, *ibid.*, 1962, 1985.
6. Chakravarti and Swaminathan, *this Journal*, 1934, 11, 101.

*EXPERIMENTAL

5-Methoxyindan-1-one was prepared by modifying the procedure described earlier^{4,5}. 3-Methoxydihydrocinnamic acid⁵ (16 g.) was added to PPA, prepared from P_2O_5 (40 g.) and H_3PO_4 (40 ml, d 1.7), at 130° and the mixture stirred at that temperature for 7 mins. After cooling, crushed ice (150 g.) was added and the solution extracted repeatedly with ethyl acetate; the extract was washed successively with 2*N* sodium carbonate and water and dried (Na_2SO_4). Evaporation of the solvent left almost pure 5-methoxyindan-1-one (12.8 g., 90%), m. p. $105-107^\circ$. Crystallised from methanol it melted at 109° . (Birch *et al.*⁴ record 65% yield, m. p. 108° ; Bone and Cort⁵ report 61% yield, m. p. 111°).

2-Carboxy-5-methoxyphenylacetic Acid (I: $R=CO_2H$; $R_1=CH_2CO_2H$).—The above indanone (5 g.) was converted into 5-methoxy-2-oximinoindan-1-one (3.2 g.) by the previously reported procedure⁶ except that 17 ml of *iso*amyl nitrite was used instead of 7 ml. On crystallisation from glacial acetic acid, it melted at 221° (decomp.); lit⁶. m. p. 221° (decomp.).

The oximino compound (6 g.) was transformed into the preceding phenylacetic acid (4.5 g.), m. p. 222° (lit.⁶ m. p. 222°) by the procedure of Chakravarti and Swaminathan⁶.

Methyl 2-Methoxycarbonyl-5-methoxyphenylacetate (I: $R=CO_2Me$; $R_1=CH_2CO_2Me$).—A suspension of the preceding acid (5.75 g.) in ether was treated with an excess of ethereal diazomethane, prepared from nitrosomethylurea (20 g.), and left overnight. Evaporation of the filtered solution left an oily residue which, on distillation *in vacuo*, afforded the methyl ester as a colorless oil, b. p. $64-65^\circ/0.5$ mm, readily solidified to a mass of white needles (5.3 g., 81%), m. p. $53-54^\circ$ (lit⁷. m. p./b. p. not recorded). (Found: C, 60.3; H, 6.1. Calc. for $C_{12}H_{14}O_5$: C, 60.5; H, 5.0%).

Alternatively, a solution of the acid (I: $R=CO_2H$; $R_1=CH_2CO_2H$) (19.5 g.) in anhydrous methanol (175 ml) and H_2SO_4 (conc., 4 ml) was refluxed for 10 hours. The reaction mixture was worked up in the usual way and the oily product was purified as above to yield the above methyl ester (15.5 g., 70%), m. p. 54° , undepressed on admixture with the specimen prepared as above.

2-Hydroxymethyl-5-methoxyphenethyl Alcohol (I: $R=CH_2OH$; $R_1=CH_2CH_2OH$).—To a stirred slurry of $LiAlH_4$ (1.1 g.) in dry ether (75 ml) was added, at such a rate as to maintain reflux, a solution of the preceding ester (5.5 g.) in dry ether (75 ml). After the addition, the mixture was refluxed further for 30 mins. and set aside. Next day, water was added cautiously with stirring, followed by 2*N*- H_2SO_4 , to produce a clear solution. The ether layer was separated and the aqueous solution was extracted with ether (30 ml $\times$ 15); the combined extract was dried (Na_2SO_4) and the solvent removed. Vacuum distillation of the residue afforded a colorless oil (b. p. $174-75^\circ/0.1$ mm) which, on treatment with a little benzene, solidified to a paste of fine needles. Recrystallisations from benzene-petroleum furnished the pure alcohol (3.3 g., 78%) as colorless needles, m. p. $95-96^\circ$. (Found: C, 66.12; H, 7.80. $C_{10}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 65.94; H, 7.69%).

The *di-p-nitrobenzoate* derivative, prepared in the usual way, crystallised from methanol as white needles, m. p. 121° . (Found: N, 5.92. $C_{24}H_{20}O_8N_2$ requires N, 5.83%).

*All m. p. s. are uncorrected. Petroleum used had b. p. $60-80^\circ$, unless otherwise stated.

6-Methoxyisochroman (II).—(a). Phosphorus pentoxide (15 g.) was added portionwise to a solution of the preceding alcohol (2.7 g.) in boiling dry benzene (50 ml) and the mixture was refluxed with stirring for 1 hour. The benzene solution was decanted and combined with several benzene extracts of the gummy residue. The residue was treated with water and repeatedly extracted with ether; the ether and benzene extracts were combined, washed with 2*N* sodium carbonate and water, and dried (Na_2SO_4). Evaporation of the organic solvent left a gum which on distillation *in vacuo* afforded the isochroman as a colorless oil (1.9 g., 78%), b. p. 155°/0.15 mm. (Found: C, 73.31; H, 7.49. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 73.18; H, 7.32%).

(b). An intimate mixture of the alcohol (2 g.) and freshly fused KHSO_4 (2.5 g.) was heated for 1 hr. at 130–40° in an oil bath, the system being connected to an efficient water pump to remove most of the water formed during the reaction. Subsequent distillation of the residue under vacuum afforded the product (II) as colorless oil (1.1 g.; 61%), b. p. 154–55°/0.15 mm.

3,4-Dihydro-6-methoxyisocoumarin (III:R=H).—(a). A solution of CrO_3 (5.4 g.) in water (4.5 ml) and glacial acetic acid (18 ml) were added dropwise with stirring during 50 mins. to the preceding isochroman (II) (2.5 g.), dissolved in glacial acetic acid (75 ml), maintained at 20–22° by occasional cooling the exothermic reaction mixture with ice-water. After the addition, stirring was continued for 1 hour at that temperature and then left to attain the room temperature (33°) at which the reaction mixture was kept for 3 hours. It was next treated with water (100 ml), extracted with chloroform (50 ml $\times$ 5), the extract washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and water, and dried (Na_2SO_4). Evaporation of the chloroform left a yellow gummy residue, the benzene solution of which was chromatographed through a column of Brockmann alumina, using the same solvent as the eluent. Benzene was distilled and the solid residue, on three crystallisations from ethyl acetate-light petroleum (b. p. 40–60°), furnished the pure product (1.9 g., 70%) as colorless fine needles, m. p. 68°. (Found: C, 67.68; H, 5.87. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 67.42; H, 5.62%).

(b). A solution of the isochroman (II) (1.5 g.) in dry xylene (20 ml) was refluxed with SeO_2 (1.5 g.) for 4 hours. The xylene solution was filtered and evaporated to dryness under reduced pressure. The solid residue was dissolved in benzene and chromatographed through a column of Brockmann alumina which was eluted with the same solvent. Evaporation of the benzene left an oil which, when kept in a refrigerator for a week, solidified to a mass of slender needles, m. p. 41°. Sublimation *in vacuo*, followed by crystallisation from ethyl acetate-light petroleum (b. p. 40–60°) yielded the pure compound (0.9 g., 55%), m. p. 70°, undepressed on admixture with the specimen obtained by method (a).

4-Bromo-3,4-dihydro-6-methoxyisocoumarin (III: R=Br).—A mixture of dihydroisocoumarin (III: R=H) (1.0 g.), *N*-bromosuccinimide (1.2 g.), and benzoyl peroxide (0.02 g.) in CCl_4 (25 ml) was refluxed for 1 hour close to an illuminated 60-watt lamp. More benzoyl peroxide (0.02 g.) was added and the reflux continued for 1 hour more. The yellow colour, which developed within 10 mins. after the start of the experiment, was discharged after 50 minutes of reflux. The cooled solution was filtered from succinimide which was washed with CCl_4 . The filtrate and the washings were combined, washed with 5% sodium carbonate and water, and dried (Na_2SO_4). Evaporation of the solvent left a gum which was dissolved in ethyl acetate (a few ml); addition of light petroleum, followed by ether, immediately deposited a solid (0.75 g.), m. p. 97–99°. Recrystallisation from ethyl acetate-

petroleum furnished the pure product (0.7 g., 52%) as silky white needles, m.p. 102-103°. (Found: C, 46.26; H, 3.67; Br, 30.88. $C_{10}H_9O_3Br$ requires C, 46.6; H, 3.5; Br, 31.13%).

6-Methoxyisocoumarin (IV).—The preceding compound (0.5 g.) in triethylamine (10 ml) was refluxed for 15 hours and the solid residue, left after evaporation of triethylamine, was repeatedly triturated with ice-cold 2*N*-HCl, followed by water. It was collected, dried, and purified by vacuum sublimation; subsequent crystallisation from ethyl acetate-petroleum yielded the pure compound (IV) (0.24 g. 70%), as colorless needles, m.p. 98°. (Found: C, 68.55; H, 4.93. $C_{10}H_8O_3$ requires C, 68.19; H, 4.54%).

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